

Results and Discussion

The experimental results of the present investigation are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The complex is fairly soluble in dioxane, ethanol and chloroform but sparingly soluble in ether, carbon tetrachloride and glacial acetic acid. The complex is decomposed when heated with concentrated sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids. The analytical results indicate the composition of the complex $[C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4]_2Ba$.

TABLE 1—QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF BARIUM WITH *N-m-TOLYL-m-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID*

Barium taken mg	Barium found mg	Number of determination	Standard deviation
0.687	0.686	5	±0.01
2.061	2.059	5	±0.02
3.435	3.435	6	±0.01
4.122	4.121	5	±0.01
6.870	6.869	6	±0.02
13.740	13.740	5	±0.01

TABLE 2—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BARIUM FROM FOREIGN IONS

Barium taken mg	Foreign metal ions mg	Masking Agent	Barium found
6.88	Ag ⁺⁶⁰	Cyanide	6.87
4.12	Mn ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Cyanide	4.12
4.12	Ni ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Cyanide	4.13
6.88	Cu ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	6.89
6.88	Zn ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	6.87
6.88	Cd ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	6.88
4.12	Hg ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Cyanide	4.13
4.12	Pd ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	4.12
13.74	Be ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.76
13.74	Ga ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.75
13.74	Sb ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.74
6.88	As ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	6.86
6.88	Bi ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	6.87
13.74	Ti ⁺⁴⁵⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.74
13.74	Zr ⁺⁴⁵⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.75
6.88	V ^{+5 60}	Cyanide	6.89
4.12	Mo ⁺⁶¹⁰⁰	Mg-EDTA	4.13
4.12	UO ₂ ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Mg-EDTA	4.14

Analysis :

A known amount of barium complex was decomposed with a mixture of perchloric, sulphuric and nitric acid and the barium content was determined volumetrically¹⁵. The elemental analysis show the percentage composition as below :

C = 49.47%, H = 3.27%, N = 8.23%, Ba = 20.23%, and found

C = 49.48%, H = 3.26%, N = 8.25%, Ba = 20.22%

Effect of pH :

For carrying out the separation and gravimetric determination of barium in the solutions of different

pH values with all other factors identical revealed that they are irrespective at pH 2.5–3.0 range.

Masking Agents :

Experimental study shows that the presence of the excess of Mg-EDTA and cyanide did not interfere with precipitation of barium with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid*. However oxalate and citrate inhibited the precipitation.

Precision and Accuracy :

The present investigation for the gravimetric determination of barium has the relative average error ±0.01.

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Chemical Examination of *Hesprethusa crenulata* (Roxb) Roem.

HAFIZULLAH KHAN, S. A. SIDDIQUI & ASIF ZAMAN*

Department of Research in Unani Medicine
and

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh

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H. crenulata (N.O. Rutaceae, Hindi—Beli) grows abundantly in different parts of India. The fruit, a small globose berry, is reported to diminish intestinal fermentation, to resist the contagion of

small pox, malignant and pestilent fevers and also to act as an antidote to various poisons¹. Earlier, luvangetin has been isolated from its leaves² in our laboratory. Later, isolation and characterisation of 4-methoxy-1-methyl-2-quinolone has been reported from the stem bark³. Recently, sitosterol, 4-methoxy-1-methyl-2-quinolone and four coumarins, viz., suberosin, epoxysuberosin, marmesin and suberenol were found to be present in the root bark⁴ of this plant. The present communication deals with the investigation carried out on the fruit collected from Dehra Dun.

Air dried powdered fruit was successively extracted with light petroleum and benzene. The concentrated petroleum ether extract on cooling afforded a mixture of fluorescent compounds which on column chromatography over silica gel and repeated crystallisations from petroleum ether-benzene yielded two TLC pure colourless crystalline compounds, I and II.

Compound I, m.p. 88°, analysed for C₁₅H₁₆O₃ and showed λ_{max}^{EtOH} 224, 255, 332 nm; ν_{max}^{KBr} 1748, 1656, 1250, 1136 and 835 cm⁻¹. The NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, τ values) displayed single proton doublets at 2.24 and 3.65 (J = 9.5 Hz) characteristic of the H-4 and H-3 protons of the coumarin nucleus, singlets at 2.68 and 3.12 due to H-5 and H-8, three proton singlets at 6.02 due to -OCH₃. The presence of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyl side chain was evident from one proton multiplet at 4.60, two protons doublet at 6.62 (J = 7 Hz) and six protons multiplet at 8.25. Its identity with suberosin⁵ was confirmed through co-TLC and mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample.

Compound II, m.p. 185° analysed for C₁₅H₁₄O₄, showed λ_{max}^{EtOH} 228, 251, 334 nm and ν_{max}^{KBr} 3456, 1750, 1642, 1265, 1130 and 832 cm⁻¹. Its NMR spectrum besides showing the presence of H-4 (2.38, d, J = 9.5 Hz), H-3 (3.76, d, J = 9.5 Hz), H-5 (2.75, s) and H-8 (3.25, s) protons of the coumarin nucleus exhibited a two proton doublet at 6.75 (J = 9 Hz), single proton triplet at 5.20 (J = 9 Hz), two three proton singlets at 8.62 and 8.76 and one broad single proton singlet at 8.04 which disappeared on D₂O shake. It was identified as marmesin⁶ by direct comparison (TLC, mixed m.p.) with an authentic sample.

The benzene extract on concentration and several crystallisations of the product afforded a better principle, m.p. 298°, C₂₆H₃₀O₈, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 213 nm. Its IR spectrum, ν_{max}^{KBr} 1765 (broad, lactone), 1718 (> C = O), 1512 and 882 cm⁻¹ (β -substituted furan)⁷ and a positive Ehrlich test⁸ indicated the presence of an intact furan ring. The chemotaxonomic study has shown frequent occurrence of limonoid bitters in Rutaceae⁹. In the light of these facts the compound was suspected to be a limonoid. The study of its mass spectrum, m/e 470 (2.7%, M⁺), 413 (16.3%), 348 (74%), 347 (100%), 331 (15.4%), 329 (16.3%), 137 (18.1%), 136 (30%), 135 (45.9%), 121 (29.5%), 119 (23.3%), 109 (29.5%), 108 (49.1%), 107 (30.4%), 97 (34.2%) and 95 (64.5%) gave inference of its being limonin¹⁰. Final confirmation was achieved by mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample of limonin.

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